

ENERGY,
the only “currency” that makes
sense in humanity's future

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This light paper tackles how our monetary system works, and how we can make it better and equitable using blockchain and a new hypothetical global currency.

Introduction

In the grand tapestry of human civilization, the evolution of currency has been a defining thread, shaping economies, societies, and the fabric of our interactions. From the barter systems of antiquity to the complex financial instruments of today, our monetary systems have continually adapted to the needs and challenges of their times. Yet, as we stand on the precipice of unprecedented global challenges climate change, resource scarcity, and economic inequality it's evident that our current financial paradigms are ill-equipped to guide us toward a sustainable and equitable future.

As we stand on the brink of innovation we find ourselves with the necessary tools to build a more robust financial system that will change everything.

This paper is going to blow your mind and make you think about “specious value” and “true value”.

Energy as a currency

Energy, unlike fiat currency, is a universal constant. It underpins every facet of our existence, from the food we eat to the devices we use and the societies we build. By conceptualizing energy as the foundational unit of a new global currency, we can create a system that is inherently fair, transparent, and sustainable.

Imagine the Energy is represented in your wallet as any other currency and has all great qualities:

- **Acceptability:** A currency must be widely accepted as a means of payment for goods and services.
- **Portability:** A currency must be easy to carry and transfer from one person to another, facilitating trade and transactions.
- **Divisibility:** A currency should be divisible into smaller units to accommodate transactions of varying sizes, allowing for both large and small purchases.
- **Uniformity:** Each unit of the currency must be the same as every other unit. This uniformity ensures that each unit is interchangeable, making transactions straightforward and fair.
- **Limited Supply:** To maintain its value, a currency must have a limited supply. If a currency can be produced in unlimited quantities, it risks devaluation and inflation.
- **Fungibility:** Each unit of the currency must be capable of mutual substitution with other units. This means that any one unit is indistinguishable from another and can be used interchangeably.
- **Recognizability:** The currency must be easily recognizable and difficult to counterfeit. This ensures trust in the currency and prevents fraud.

Let's think of our currency in digital for now...

Current Monetary Systems

The evolution of monetary systems has played an important role in shaping economies and societies throughout history. While modern

monetary systems have facilitated unprecedented economic growth and development, they also exhibit significant flaws that challenge their sustainability and fairness. This section examines the strengths and weaknesses of contemporary monetary systems.

Medium of Exchange:

Modern currencies simplify transactions by eliminating the inefficiencies of barter systems, enabling seamless trade on local, national, and global scales.

Standard of Value:

They provide a common measure of value, making it easier to compare prices and value goods and services consistently.

Capital Formation:

Efficient monetary systems encourage savings and investments, leading to capital accumulation and economic growth.

Global Trade:

Currencies enable international trade by providing a means to value and exchange goods and services across borders, fostering global economic integration.

Weaknesses of Current Monetary Systems

While modern monetary systems have undoubtedly contributed to economic progress and development, they are not without significant flaws. **Inflation, centralization of control, resource misallocation, and environmental impact** are pressing issues that need to be addressed. As we look to the future, there is a growing need to reimagine our monetary systems to create a more equitable, sustainable, and resilient economic framework.

This paper does not propose replacing the current monetary system but suggests implementing an alternative system to address its flaws.

Inflation:

Poorly managed monetary policies can lead to inflation, diminishing the purchasing power of money and causing instability. Excessive money supply without corresponding economic growth often results in higher prices for goods and services, affecting the economy adversely.

Centralization of Control:

Central banks and governments have substantial control over monetary systems, which can lead to policy mismanagement and abuse of power. This centralization reduces transparency and can result in decisions that benefit a few at the expense of the broader population.

Resource Misallocation:

Current monetary systems can drive speculative bubbles and short-term profit pursuits, leading to inefficient allocation of resources. This misallocation often neglects long-term sustainability and can cause economic instability when bubbles burst.

Environmental Impact:

The focus on economic growth within existing monetary frameworks often incentivizes the over-exploitation of natural resources, contributing to environmental degradation and climate change. Sustainable practices are frequently overlooked, endangering future generations' well-being.

The Proposal

This paper proposes a new system that leverages blockchain technology and an energy-based currency to address the critical weaknesses of inflation, centralization of control, resource misallocation, and environmental impact. This system aims to create a more equitable, transparent, and sustainable economic framework.

Energy-Based Currency:

- **Intrinsic Value:** Unlike fiat currencies, an energy-based currency would be tied to a tangible resource—energy. This intrinsic value helps stabilize the currency and protect against inflation.
- **Controlled Supply:** The issuance of energy-based currency can be closely regulated based on actual energy production, preventing the excessive supply that leads to inflation.

Blockchain Integration:

- **Transparency:** Blockchain technology ensures that all transactions are transparent and immutable, allowing for real-time monitoring of currency supply and preventing unauthorized changes.
- **Smart Contracts:** Automated contracts can regulate currency issuance and circulation, maintaining a balance between supply and demand and further reducing inflationary pressures.

Implementing an energy-based currency on a blockchain platform offers a comprehensive solution to the key weaknesses of current monetary systems. This new approach can combat inflation, decentralize control, correct resource misallocation, and mitigate environmental impact, paving the way for a more equitable, transparent, and sustainable economic future. By integrating these innovative technologies and principles, we can build a financial system that truly serves the long-term interests of humanity and the planet.

Practical Solution

To address the various issues inherent in current monetary systems, our approach involves building a blockchain that directly tackles these challenges.

Tackling Energy Consumption in Blockchain Technology

First, we must address the significant energy consumption typically associated with blockchain technology. Traditional consensus algorithms, such as Proof of Work (PoW), are notoriously energy-intensive and environmentally unsustainable. To overcome this, we have developed a new consensus algorithm.

Introducing Proof of Energy Generation

Our innovative consensus algorithm, Proof of Energy Generation (PoEG), is designed to minimize energy consumption. Instead of relying on the energy-demanding processes of PoW, PoEG harnesses renewable energy production. By replacing PoW with PoEG, we effectively solve the energy consumption problem and align the blockchain's operational incentives with environmental sustainability and renewable energy adoption.

How it works

First, let's use a model that's easy to relate to: a solar system with a sun and its orbiting planets.

In this analogy, think of our blockchain like a solar system. The sun represents the main node that keeps track of the global network's rank. Planets, in this context, represent other nodes within the blockchain, and satellites are the energy producers connected to these nodes.

Each satellite (energy producer) reports its energy production at set intervals to its corresponding planet (node). The planets accumulate this information and maintain a record of the total energy generated within their network. This data aggregation is crucial for the overall transparency and accountability of the system.

The main node (sun) evaluates which nodes (planets) have the highest cumulative energy. This ranking determines which node has the opportunity to solve a transaction on the blockchain. When a node successfully writes a new block to the blockchain, it uses some of its accumulated hypothetical energy. In return, it receives a reward for its efforts, ensuring motivation for continued participation.

After a node is rewarded, it must pay the energy producers (satellites) based on the amount of energy they have contributed. This payment is proportional to the energy each producer has generated, contributing to the node's overall score. By distributing rewards in this manner, the system ensures that all participants are fairly compensated for their contributions, promoting a balanced and efficient energy production and consumption cycle.

To prevent bottlenecks, this system allows other nodes to have the chance to add blocks to the blockchain after the energy of the leading node is partially depleted by block writing. This rotation encourages a fair and efficient distribution of opportunities across the network, enhancing the overall performance and preventing any single node from monopolizing blockchain activities.

By employing this model, we ensure a balanced and sustainable approach to blockchain operations, integrating renewable energy generation with decentralized transaction validation, thus promoting an eco-friendly and efficient blockchain ecosystem.

NOTE: *The energy is not consumed by the system; instead, the system merely tracks the energy produced by its participants. These energy metrics are used to create a fair and secure functionality within the blockchain. When we refer to energy being "depleted," it simply means the system is using these recorded numbers to maintain balance and fairness, without actually consuming energy from the producers.*

Blockchain rep. Img. 1

Blockchain rep. Img. 2

The diagrams represent a hierarchical structure of the blockchain network, illustrating the flow of energy data and the validation process from energy producers (satellites) to the central coordinating node (Sun Master Node).

Explanation of the Diagram

Satellite (EP1) - Energy Producer:

Role: Individual energy-producing entities, such as solar systems with inverters.

Function: These satellites generate renewable energy. In this example, EP1 produces 3 kW of energy and reports this production to the Planet Node (P1).

Planet (P1) - Node:

Role: Intermediate nodes that collect and aggregate energy data from multiple satellites.

Function: P1 collects the energy production data from its connected satellites (e.g., EP1, EP2, etc.). In this example, P1 has aggregated a total of 120 kW of energy from all its connected satellites. It then reports this total energy production to the Sun Master Node.

Sun Master Node:

Role: The central coordinating node in the network.

Function: The Sun Master Node maintains a global rank of all planet nodes based on their cumulative energy production. It uses this information to determine which node gets to validate transactions and write new blocks to the blockchain. For example, P1 with 120 kW, P2 with 80 kW, and so on.

Workflow

Energy Reporting: Satellites (EP1, EP2, etc.) generate energy and report their production to their respective Planet Node (P1).

Data Aggregation: The Planet Node (P1) aggregates the energy data from its connected satellites and maintains a total energy production record (120 kW in this case).

Global Ranking: The Sun Master Node evaluates the energy data from all Planet Nodes to rank them based on their cumulative energy production.

Validation Opportunity: The node with the highest cumulative energy gets the opportunity to validate transactions and write a new block to the blockchain.

Reward Distribution: After a node successfully writes a block, it receives a reward. The node then distributes this reward among its connected energy producers based on their contributions.

Key Points

Energy Tracking: The system tracks the energy produced by participants without consuming it. The recorded energy data is used to maintain a fair and secure functionality within the blockchain.

Preventing Bottlenecks: By rotating the block-writing opportunities among nodes based on their energy contributions, the system prevents any single node from monopolizing blockchain activities.

Sustainable Incentives: This model promotes the generation of renewable energy by rewarding energy producers, thereby supporting environmental sustainability and reducing the carbon footprint.

By implementing this structure, the protocol ensures a balanced and efficient blockchain ecosystem that integrates renewable energy generation with decentralized transaction validation.

Mathematical Model for Our System

Total Energy Provided by Satellites

The total energy produced by a Planet Node (E_p) is the sum of all the energy produced by its connected satellites (E_{EPi})

$$E_p = \sum_{i=1}^n E_{EPi}$$

E_p is the total energy produced by the Planet Node.

E_{EPi} is the energy produced by the i -th Satellite Energy Producer.

n is the total energy produced by the Planet Node.

Energy Decrease When a Block is Minted

The updated energy for the Planet Node after minting a block can be calculated as follows:

$$E_p' = E_p - E_B$$

E_p is the total energy produced by the Planet Node before minting.

E_B is the total energy cost associated with minting the new block.

E_p' is the remaining energy of the Planet Node after minting.

Energy Cost per Block

The total energy cost for minting a block (E_B) is the sum of the energy costs for all individual transactions within that block.

$$E_B = \sum_{i=1}^n E_{TXi}$$

E_B is the total energy cost for the block.

E_{TXi} is the energy cost for the i -th transaction.

n is the total number of transactions in the block.

These formulas ensure the system efficiently tracks the energy produced by the participants, promoting fair validation opportunities and supporting a sustainable blockchain ecosystem.

Real-World Applications of Our System

By integrating blockchain technology with renewable energy generation, this system offers numerous real-world applications. Here are some practical implementations:

Decentralized Energy Markets:

This system can facilitate decentralized energy markets where individuals and businesses trade renewable energy. Producers can sell excess energy directly to consumers using tokens, promoting efficient energy distribution and reducing reliance on centralized energy providers.

Energy Surplus Management:

By incentivizing renewable energy generation, this system can help create a surplus of energy. This surplus can be stored or redistributed, reducing the risk of energy shortages. Surplus energy can also be utilized in times of high demand, ensuring a stable energy supply.

Universal Basic Income (UBI) via Energy Production:

This system can contribute to a form of universal basic income by rewarding individuals for generating renewable energy. Participants receive tokens for their energy contributions, providing a steady income stream and promoting financial stability, particularly in underserved communities.

Transparent and Efficient Energy Subsidies:

Governments and organizations can use this system to implement transparent and efficient energy subsidy programs. By distributing subsidies in the form of tokens, they can ensure that funds are used specifically for renewable energy generation, enhancing the effectiveness of such programs.

Sustainable Business Models:

Businesses can adopt this system to develop sustainable business models. For instance, companies with large renewable energy infrastructures can earn additional revenue by selling excess energy and receiving rewards for their contributions to the grid, promoting environmental responsibility and profitability.

Smart Grids and IoT Integration:

Integrating this system with smart grids and Internet of Things (IoT) devices can enhance energy management. Smart meters and IoT sensors can provide real-time data on energy production and consumption, enabling dynamic pricing and efficient energy allocation.

Community-Based Renewable Projects:

This system can support community-based renewable energy projects by pooling resources and rewarding collective energy generation. Communities can collaborate to install solar panels or wind turbines and share the benefits through tokens, fostering local sustainability initiatives.

Carbon Credits and Environmental Impact Tracking:

This system can facilitate the issuance and trading of carbon credits. By tracking renewable energy generation and consumption, it can provide verifiable data for carbon offset programs, encouraging businesses and individuals to reduce their carbon footprints.

These applications showcase how this system can drive innovation in energy management, promote sustainability, and contribute to financial stability through decentralized and transparent mechanisms.

Naming the EGO Protocol

We named our system the "EGO Protocol" as a playful yet meaningful connection between ego and money. In psychology, the ego represents self-worth, reflecting the value tied to energy and economic transactions in our financial system. Additionally, EGO stands for "Energy Generation Opportunities," capturing our mission to reward sustainable energy contributions. This name underscores our goal to align individual actions with broader environmental stewardship.

Conclusion

In the grand narrative of human progress, our monetary systems have long served as the bedrock of economic activity and societal development. However, the evolving landscape of global challenges demands innovative solutions that address the flaws of traditional financial frameworks. This paper has explored the transformative potential of integrating blockchain technology with an energy-based currency to create a more equitable, transparent, and sustainable economic system.

This protocol stands at the forefront of this revolution. By leveraging the Proof of Energy Generation (PoEG) consensus algorithm, we not only mitigate the excessive energy consumption associated with traditional blockchain models but also incentivize the production of renewable energy. This innovative approach addresses key issues such as inflation, centralization of control, resource misallocation, and environmental impact.

Our proposed system ensures that energy contributions are fairly tracked and rewarded. This decentralized and transparent method fosters a balanced distribution of validation opportunities, preventing bottlenecks and promoting a sustainable cycle of energy generation and blockchain validation.

As we look to the future, the integration of renewable energy production with decentralized financial systems offers a visionary path forward. The protocol exemplifies how technological advancements can be harnessed to create a financial ecosystem that not only drives economic growth but also supports environmental sustainability and social equity.

By reimagining currency as a reflection of our most critical resource—energy—we pave the way for a financial system that truly serves the long-term interests of humanity and the planet. The Energy Generation Opportunity (EGO) Protocol shows us a fresh perspective in this energy era, moving towards a future where sustainability, transparency, and fairness are the cornerstones of our global economy.

Together, we can build a world where economic activity aligns with the principles of sustainability and equity, ensuring a prosperous and harmonious future for generations to come.

Declarations:

Ethics approval and consent to participate

This study did not involve human participants, human data, or human tissue, and therefore did not require ethical approval. As this research focuses on the development and implementation of a blockchain-based renewable energy generation system, all data used in the study pertains to energy production and blockchain transactions, which do not involve ethical concerns related to human subjects.

If there are any questions or concerns regarding the ethical aspects of this research, please do not hesitate to contact the corresponding author.

Consent for publication

The only author of this manuscript has read and approved the final version of the paper. I the author of this manuscript consent to the publication in Springer Nature - Energy, Sustainability and Society journal, should it be accepted.

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Your feedback and support are invaluable as we work towards a future where sustainability, transparency, and fairness are the cornerstones of our global economy.

Sincerely,

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